

Impact of Artificial Intelligence on International Trade

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Abstract

In this research, the economic dimensions of Artificial Intelligence in international trade have been explored. Trade consists of the roles of scale and competition, which is also export and import procedure and documentation. This research includes the key features of AI with respect to these dimensions and explains the features of international trade in respect of AI. The objective of research is to find the impact on exporters and importers due to usage of Artificial Intelligence in International Trade.

The pros and cons of Artificial Intelligence on international trade will also be spotted in this research. A combination of primary and secondary data collection has been used for the research. Besides, how the policies are implemented with respect to research, standards and competition to improve AI in International Trade.

At last, our study will also be helpful in emphasizing that there is still long way to go and much to learn before we have a comprehensive understanding of how Artificial Intelligence will affect international trade.

Keywords : Artificial intelligence, international trade, procedure, documentation and competition.

Introduction

Artificial intelligence means machine intelligence, is intelligence demonstrated by machines, in contrast to natural intelligence displayed by humans. Artificial intelligence in international trade

Export Import documentation is an important area of international trade. Documentation formalities are required to protect the interest of the buyer and the seller. They are necessary to enable the exporter to get sale value as well as to secure export incentives and the importer to get the contracted goods. The import and export procedure can be eased by the Artificial Intelligence process. And in the same way the documentation can be made easier with the help of Artificial Intelligence. Documentation is the main pillar of the foreign traded. The work of documentation is the most time consuming. Hence in order to reduce the time in documentation process, the government has made some innovative changes related to Artificial Intelligence.

In the new Foreign Trade Policy (FTP) 2015-20, the government has taken various measures under the various provisions of the policy to ease the trade procedure and documentation process. These measures have been taken by the Government in the direction of trade facilitation.

Objectives

- To find that, to what extent government has included artificial intelligence in International trade.
- To find whether exporters and importers find online procedures user friendly or not.
- To get the opinions of exporters and importers on any changes in online procedure of trade and documentation.
- To find whether corruption in trade procedure and documentation still exists after introduction of online technology.

Hypothesis

- H1 - Artificial Intelligence is useful for Exporters and Importers in International Trade.
- H0 - Artificial Intelligence is not useful for Exporters and Importers in International Trade.

Methodology

1. Sample Size - 30
2. Sample Unit - Managers
3. Sampling Technique - Convenience Sampling.
4. Sampling Frame - Different parts of India.
5. Collection of Data - Schedule.
6. Analysis of Data - Pie-charts, Bar Graph.

Measures to Simplify the Trade Procedure through Artificial Intelligence

The following measures have been taken by the Central Government through Foreign Trade Policy (FTP) 2015 – 20, in order to simplify the trade procedure through Artificial Intelligence.

1. Consultancy Services by DGFT

Online consultancy services would be provided to various Export promotion council (EPC) and Trade and industry bodies on regular basis by DGFT (Directorate General of Foreign Trade)

2. Nirayat Bandhu Scheme

Nirayat Bandhu Scheme has been launched by DGFT for monitoring new and potential exporters on the intricacies of foreign trade. The online helpdesk facility through online chat and live Q&A sessions are available.

Besides IIFT is also running online certificate program in export and import business under Nirayat Bandhu Scheme. This scheme was promoted under Digital India and Skill India Program

3. Citizen Charter

An online Citizens Charter have been created by DGFT for giving time schedule for providing various services to clients.

4. Online Compliant Registration And Monitoring System

DGFT, on its website has provided the facility of “EDI Help Desk” accessible for all the

exporters which could help them in assistance of filing online applications. It is also helpful in clarification of any other difficulties or technical problems faced during online filing of applications. For that purpose, DGFT has provided a helpline number 1800 111 55 and e-mail id. – dgftedi@nic.in

5. Online Filing of Applications

The Regional Centres of DGFT have been equipped with hi-speed internet facility under EDI plan of the Government. The importers and exporters can obtain Import Export Code No. and other related documents online. DGFT is the foremost government organization to introduce digital signature which is encrypted to the significant level of 2048 bit. Hence application and payment of fees can also be done online.

6. Online Inter-Ministerial Consultation

All kind of needed documents can also be uploaded online by the exporters and importers. Except few architectural and machine drawings, the exporters need not submit the hard copy of that document, mainly due to its nature. The processing of the applications will also be done online.

7. Enhance EDISystem

An enhanced EDI system has been developed and put into work by DGFT, for the purpose of export facilitation and good governance. This has reduced the physical interface of exporters and importers with the Government Departments and is a significant measure in the direction of reduction of transaction cost.

8. Message Exchange with Community Partner

Customs, Banks, Export Promotion Councils (EPCs) are major community partners of DGFT for message exchange. An effective message exchange system is in place with various community partners.

9. Encouraging Development of Third Party API

The development of Third party API (Application Program Interface) software is being encouraged by DGFT. It will help in integration of multiple users with DGFT through interface.

10. Other E-Governance Initiatives

An online payment gateway has been developed for the payment of application fees under FTP through debit and credit card
Mobile application has also been developed for FTP.

Measures to Simplify Documentation Process Through Artificial Intelligence

In view of, Foreign Trade Policy (2015 – 20), the following measures have been taken by the Central Government in order to simplify the documentation process and make filing of those documents easier by the exporters and importers.

1. Issue of an E– IEC

Importer Exporter Code (IEC) is the most important document for exporters and importers for international trade. DGFT has launched the facility of issuing Importer Exporter Code in

electronic form which is known as “e-IEC”. The application for e-EIC can be done online on the portal of DGFT (<http://dgft.gov.in>). The documents needed can be uploaded online and the fee payment for the same can also be done online.

2. Issue of E-BRC

One prominent initiative in recent times has been the e-BRC (Electronic Bank Realisation Certificate) project and its successful implementation by DGFT. It has enabled DGFT to capture details of realisation of export proceeds directly from the Banks through secured electronic mode. This has facilitated the implementation of various export promotion schemes without any physical interface with the stake holders.

3. Profile of Importers and Exporters

An electronic procedure has been created to upload various documents in exporter importer profile. Once uploaded, there will be no need to submit these documents / copies of these documents to Regional Authority repeatedly with each application. It intends to reduce the transaction cost and time and is a step towards paperless processing of different applications in DGFT.

4. Reduction In Mandatory Documents

The hardcopy of the documents required compulsorily for export and import have been reduced significantly upto only three documents.

5. Facility to Upload Documents

The documents like ANF 3B, ANF 3C, and ANF 3D can be uploaded digitally, duly signed by Chartered Accountant, Company Secretary or Cost Accountant. This is a move towards paperless processing of documents for an efficient and quick system of completion of an Export Order.

6. Other Initiatives

Export obligation Discharge Certificate (EODC) now can be issued online to the exporter. Message exchange system has been developed for information of CIN and DIN with Ministry of Corporate Affair.

Findings and Discussion

Chart 1.1 Showing the benefits of Artificial intelligence to Exporters and Importer

Inference

The above graph shows whether the Artificial Intelligence is beneficial to Importers and Exporters. 97% of our respondents have responded Yes followed by 3% respondents who didn't had any opinion.

Chart 1.2. Showing the % of exporters and importers doing documentation process online

Inference

The above graph shows whether the respondents are indulged in online documentation process or not. 83% our respondents have responded Yes followed by 17% respondents who have responded No.

Chart 1.3 Showing the Easiness of Online Process of Documentation

Inference

The above graph shows whether the online procedure of documentation is easier or not. 90% of our respondents have responded yes, followed by 10% respondents who have responded no.

Chart 1.4 Showing the Artificial Intelligence has made the Procedure of Export Import Easier

Inference

The above graph shows whether the online procedure of international trade has become easier or not. 90% of our respondents have responded yes, followed by 10% respondents who have responded no.

Chart 1.5 - Showing the Online trade Procedure and Documentation in Import and Export has Reduced Corruption in India in the Field of International Trade

Inference

The above graph shows whether the online trade procedure and documentation in import and export has reduced corruption in India in the fields of international trade or not. 63% of our respondents have responded yes, followed by 23% respondents who have responded no and 14% didn't had any opinion.

Chart 1.5 Showing the duty drawback in time through Online process for Importers and Exporters

Inference

The above graph shows whether the exporters and importers are getting duty draw back on time through online process or not. 7% of our respondent have responded yes, followed by 70% have responded with negative answer and 23% have responded that only sometimes they get the duty drawback in prescribed time.

Suggestions

The artificial intelligence have both advantages and disadvantages. From this research we can suggest that International trade through the online process is overall beneficial and easy, but it should become more easier and user friendly. Proper information should be given to the exporters and importers. And duty draw back to Importers and Exporters through online process in time should be properly given. And the hindrances of corruption still exists wherever human interference is there.

Conclusions

In the International trade the artificial intelligence play an important role in Importing and Exporting. Many of the Importers and Exporters are using online process in the documentation and overall international trade procedures. The trade related documentation and procedure are done through online process but there is a vast scope of improvement in it. It is very useful to the importers and exporters, saves the time, which is a crucial factor in international trade. Hence, the better Artificial Intelligence and giving it's training to the exporters and importers is the only solution to increase the volume of international trade, especially for progressively developing country like India.

Web Sources

- Foreign Trade Policy 2015-20
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- <http://niryatbandhu.iift.ac.in/main.asp>
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